

Measuring Scientific Attitude in Adolescent Science Students of Pakistan: An Empirical study of Curiosity and Rationality

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Abstract

This study investigated the scientific attitude of secondary school science students in Faisalabad, Pakistan, with a specific focus on the dimensions of curiosity and rationality. Scientific attitude is globally recognized as a vital learning outcome of science education, yet it is under-explored in South Asian contexts where cultural beliefs and socioeconomic disparities may influence students' dispositions. A quantitative descriptive survey design was employed. The sample consisted of 162 Grade 10 male science students drawn from four public secondary schools using cluster and proportionate random sampling. Data were collected using a validated Likert-scale questionnaire (5-point scale), comprising items measuring curiosity and rationality. Reliability was established through pilot testing, with Cronbach's alpha = 0.719, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Data were analyzed using SPSS, applying descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, and Pearson correlation. Results indicated that students demonstrated a moderate level of curiosity (grand mean = 3.54), with stronger interest in observable phenomena (e.g.,

digestion processes, pandemic-related science) than in abstract scientific concepts. The rationality dimension also reflected a moderate level (grand mean = 3.42); however, endorsement of cultural superstitions (e.g., omens and myths) revealed an incomplete adoption of evidence-based reasoning. Pearson correlation analysis showed significant positive relationships between curiosity and rationality ($r = .707, p < .01$), curiosity and overall scientific attitude ($r = .607, p < .01$), and rationality and overall scientific attitude ($r = .669, p < .01$). The findings suggest that while scientific curiosity is emerging among students, rationality remains hindered by persistent superstitions. Both constructs are strongly interrelated and crucial to the development of scientific literacy. The study highlights the need for inquiry-based learning strategies, teacher training to counter pseudo scientific beliefs, and equitable access to resources to foster scientific dispositions. Policymakers and educators must prioritize integrating critical thinking and

curiosity-driven pedagogy into science curricula. The study was limited to male students in public schools in Faisalabad and relied on self-reported data.

Keywords: *Scientific Attitude, Curiosity, Rationality, Secondary Education, Pakistan, Science Education, Student Attitudes*

Introduction

In the 21st century, fostering a scientific attitude in learners has become a crucial objective of science education worldwide. A scientific attitude is not merely the accumulation of scientific knowledge, but a disposition to think critically, question assumptions, remain curious, and approach problems rationally (Mangal & Mangal, 2013). As science and technology become increasingly central to economic and social development, the cultivation of these attitudes in adolescents is especially vital, particularly in developing countries such as Pakistan where education systems continue to face issues of rote learning and examination-centered teaching (Ali & Zaman, 2021).

Scientific attitude refers to a composite of traits that include curiosity, rationality, objectivity, open-mindedness, and suspended judgment (Chadha, 2005). These attributes are essential not only for scientific inquiry but for developing critical, independent thinkers capable of making informed decisions in everyday life. Among the dimensions of scientific attitude, curiosity and rationality have been identified as particularly foundational during adolescence a phase marked by increased cognitive engagement and identity exploration (Byrnes, 2020).

Curiosity, as a dimension of scientific attitude, is defined as a desire to acquire new knowledge and explore unknown phenomena (Engel, 2015). It motivates learners to ask questions, seek explanations, and engage more deeply with science content.

Rationality, on the other hand, involves logical reasoning, evidence-based thinking, and the ability to make objective judgments (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). It is a key determinant of how learners approach scientific problems and evaluate evidence.

While many studies have examined achievement in science, far fewer have explored the attitudinal dimensions that underpin student engagement and scientific thinking. In the context of Pakistan, especially in regions such as Faisalabad, science education remains largely content-driven, with little emphasis on cultivating inquisitive or analytical dispositions among students (Akram & Malik, 2020). This gap is significant given the rising demand for youth capable of contributing to scientific and technological innovation. Therefore, the present study seeks to measure the development of scientific attitudes particularly curiosity and rationality among Grade 10 science students in secondary schools in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Understanding the extent to which these attitudes are nurtured can inform both curriculum reforms and pedagogical practices in science classrooms.

Significance of the Study

In an era increasingly shaped by scientific innovation and evidence-based decision-making, the cultivation of a scientific attitude in students has emerged as a cornerstone of modern education. Scientific attitude encompasses a set of cognitive and affective dispositions such as curiosity, rationality, objectivity, and critical thinking that enable individuals to approach problems logically, question assumptions, and engage in inquiry-driven learning (Mangal & Mangal, 2013). Among these, curiosity and rationality are particularly vital during adolescence, a period characterized by cognitive expansion and the formation of lifelong learning habits (Byrnes, 2020).

Despite growing international emphasis on science education reforms, there is limited empirical data from Pakistan particularly from urban centers like Faisalabad regarding the extent to which school students possess or develop these critical scientific dispositions. In many Pakistani classrooms, science education remains primarily content-driven, emphasizing memorization over inquiry, with insufficient attention given to the attitudinal or dispositional outcomes of learning (Ali & Zaman, 2021). This study is significant because it seeks to quantitatively measure the scientific attitude of Grade 10 science students through a structured survey focusing on two core dimensions: Curiosity: the student's desire to explore, question, and seek new information, and Rationality: the student's tendency to rely on logic, evidence, and critical reasoning when evaluating ideas or solving problems. By using a quantitative survey instrument, the study aims to provide statistically valid insights into the development of these attitudes across a sample of adolescent science learners. The results will not only contribute to academic discourse in science education but also provide actionable data for educational policymakers, curriculum developers, and teacher educators in Pakistan.

Need of the Study

Furthermore, understanding the presence or absence of these dimensions can assist in diagnosing gaps in the instructional strategies, school environments, and learning cultures that shape student engagement with science. It can also inform the design of interventions that promote scientific thinking, moving education beyond rote learning towards fostering critical and inquisitive learners. In short, the need for this study arises from the imperative to build scientifically literate societies, beginning at the secondary school level. By grounding the inquiry in a local context and focusing on measurable constructs, this research provides an important step toward that broader educational and societal goal.

Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the level of curiosity as a dimension of scientific attitude among Grade 10 science students in Faisalabad.
2. To measure the level of rationality as a dimension of scientific attitude among Grade 10 science students in Faisalabad.

Research Questions

1. To what extent is curiosity developed among Grade 10 science students in Faisalabad?

- To what extent is rationality developed among Grade 10 science students in Faisalabad?

Limitations of the Study

- ◆ The study is based on self-reported data through questionnaires, which may be influenced by social desirability bias.
- ◆ Only Grade 10 science students were included; attitudes in other grades or among non-science students were not assessed.

Literature Review

Scientific attitude refers to a set of mental dispositions essential for scientific thinking and inquiry, including curiosity, rationality, objectivity, open-mindedness, and critical-mindedness (Mangal & Mangal, 2013). It is not just a by-product of learning science content but a deliberate educational goal, especially in secondary education, where foundational cognitive and attitudinal skills are developed. Scientific attitude serves as the affective foundation for scientific literacy defined not only by the knowledge of scientific facts but also by the ability to engage in reasoned judgment, problem-solving, and critical evaluation of evidence (Bybee, 2010).

Figure: 1

Main components of scientific attitude

Figure 1: Main components of scientific attitude based on the previous studies

Developing a scientific attitude is central to creating a scientifically literate society capable of engaging with contemporary global challenges such as climate change, health crises, and technological change. Research shows that students with strong scientific attitudes are more

likely to pursue science careers, engage in lifelong learning, and exhibit higher academic performance in science (Osborne, Simon, & Collins, 2003; Rocard et al., 2007).

In the context of developing countries, particularly South Asia, cultivating such attitudes can help counteract rote learning, promote critical inquiry, and bridge the gap between science education and real-world application (Ali & Shabbir, 2020; Safdar et al., 2021). Curiosity is broadly defined as a learner's intrinsic desire to acquire new knowledge and explore unknown phenomena. It is widely acknowledged as a motivational engine for science learning and is linked with inquiry-based learning strategies (Engel, 2015). Engel (2011) emphasizes that encouraging curiosity in educational settings leads to deeper engagement and greater conceptual understanding. However, several studies note that formal schooling often suppresses curiosity through rigid curricula and exam-oriented teaching (Ramani & Siegler, 2008; Engel, 2015). In Pakistani classrooms, Ali and Zaman (2021) found that students were rarely given opportunities to ask open-ended questions or explore content beyond the textbook, leading to low levels of curiosity among learners.

Rationality, in the context of scientific attitude, refers to the ability to apply logic, evidence-based reasoning, and systematic thinking when approaching problems. It includes the rejection of superstition, emotional reasoning, and unsupported beliefs (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). Studies such as Taconis, Ferguson-Hessler, and Broekkamp (2001) indicate that rational thinking in science learners is positively correlated with higher-order cognitive skills, including problem-solving and critical evaluation.

In science education, rationality enables students to evaluate competing hypotheses, draw justified conclusions, and avoid biases skills increasingly recognized as necessary for global citizenship (NRC, 2012). Unfortunately, in many secondary schools in Pakistan, rationality is not explicitly taught or assessed. Teachers tend to focus on factual recall, and classroom discussions rarely include logical argumentation or counter-evidence evaluation (Akram & Malik, 2020).

In light of the critical role curiosity and rationality play, it is useful to conceptualize scientific attitude as a multi-dimensional construct comprising cognitive, affective, and behavioral dispositions. These components interact synergistically: curiosity fuels the desire to explore, while rationality provides the tools for logical evaluation and skepticism. Together, they form the foundation for scientific literacy, empowering students not only to understand scientific content but to question misinformation, evaluate evidence, and contribute meaningfully to societal problem-solving in areas such as health, climate, and technology.

Table:1

Operational Definitions and Educational Roles of Scientific Attitude Dimensions

Dimension	Definition	Key Behaviors	Role in Science Learning
Curiosity	A desire to explore and understand new phenomena.	Asking questions, exploring, hypothesizing	Drives inquiry-based learning and motivates deeper engagement with scientific content.
Rationality	The use of logic and evidence to make decisions and solve problems.	Reasoning, analyzing, justifying with data	Helps learners evaluate claims, design experiments, and make informed conclusions.

Empirical Studies on Scientific Attitude

Various instruments have been developed to measure scientific attitude. Moore and Sutman (1970) proposed a widely used scale, while more recent works (e.g., Germann, 1988) adapted items to assess dimensions such as interest, open-mindedness, and logical thinking. In a quantitative study on Indian high school students, Chavan and Mehta (2018) found that both curiosity and rationality were underdeveloped, especially among students taught using traditional pedagogies. Similarly, Safdar et al. (2021) emphasized the need for structured interventions in Pakistan to foster inquiry-based attitudes. A review by Osborne et al. (2003) concluded that most science education reforms focus on content rather than attitude, despite the latter being a stronger predictor of long-term scientific engagement.

Gaps in the Literature

While there is extensive theoretical work on the components of scientific attitude, few empirical studies have quantitatively measured its dimensions among adolescents in South Asia, particularly Pakistan. Most studies tend to evaluate academic performance, overlooking the dispositional aspects such as curiosity and rationality. Moreover, urban centers like Faisalabad have been largely neglected in attitudinal research, despite being educational hubs with diverse school systems. This gap justifies the need for the present study, which aims to provide data-driven insights into the scientific attitudes of secondary school learners in the region.

Research Methodology

The primary objective of this study was to measure the scientific attitude of Grade 10 science students in public secondary schools in Faisalabad, Pakistan, with a particular focus on two key dimensions: curiosity and rationality. Given that scientific attitude is considered a foundational outcome of science education globally (Mangal & Mangal, 2013), it is critical to evaluate the

extent to which these attitudes are developed among adolescent learners in a developing country context.

Pakistan, located in South Asia, is the world’s sixth most populous country, with a population exceeding 200 million. Approximately 50% of the population is under the age of 20, highlighting the importance of investment in education, especially science education. Despite improvements in literacy, national indicators suggest significant gaps in critical thinking and scientific reasoning among students (Ali & Shabbir, 2020). Punjab is the largest and most populous province of Pakistan, with a literacy rate of approximately 63% as per the Economic Survey (2015). The province has a diverse mix of rural and urban districts and is home to several prominent educational institutions.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design, which is suitable for assessing attitudes, perceptions, and traits within a defined population (Borg & Gall, 1998). This design allowed for the quantitative measurement of scientific attitude, particularly the dimensions of curiosity and rationality, through the administration of a structured questionnaire.

Population

The population comprised all male science students enrolled in public sector secondary schools in Faisalabad city. According to official records, there are 33 boys’ secondary schools in the city (Punjab, School Department 2020).

Sample and Sampling Technique

Due to resource constraints, the study was delimited to four public secondary schools. A total student population of 905 in the selected schools served as the accessible population. The sample size of 162 students was determined using a sample size calculator and selected using a cluster sampling technique, followed by proportionate random sampling within schools.

Table: 2

Cluster-Wise Distribution of Sample from Public Secondary Schools in Faisalabad City

Boy’s science students of secondary schools in Faisalabad City.					
Sr.No	Cluster	No.	Schools Name	Population	Sample Proportional
1	Sargodha Road (Faisalabad)	1	Govt. Jamia chishtia High School, Faisalabad	166	32
		2	Govt. Crescent Model high school, Faisalabad	406	61
2	Gulam Muhammad Abad (Faisalabad)	3	Govt. High School New colony, Gulam. Muhamadabad	203	39
		4	Govt. High School. Millat-e-	151	30

			Islamia, Gulam. Muhamdabad		
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Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire comprising 10 items was developed to assess scientific attitude. The items were aligned with key dimensions identified in the literature particularly curiosity and rationality along with other related constructs such as open-mindedness, critical-mindedness, objectivity, and aversion to superstition. The questionnaire employed a Likert-scale format and was designed to reflect the objectives of the study. Items were pilot tested and refined for clarity and relevance.

Reliability and Validity

To ensure reliability, pilot testing was conducted with 8 students who were not part of the final sample. Using Cronbach's alpha, the internal consistency of the questionnaire was found to be $\alpha = 0.719$, indicating an acceptable level of reliability (Taber, 2018). Content validity was ensured through expert review and alignment with established constructs from existing scales (Moore & Sutman, 1970; Germann, 1988).

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected in person by the researcher in classroom settings. The purpose of the study was explained to all participants, and informed consent was obtained. Questionnaires were administered in a controlled environment to ensure high response rates and eliminate external distractions.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Descriptive statistics mean, standard deviation, weighted score, and percentage were used to analyze responses on the other hand, Correlation Analysis (Pearson's r) to assess the relationship between curiosity and rationality among the students. Data were organized in tabular form and responses for each scientific attitude dimension were arranged in descending order to highlight prominent trends.

Ethical Considerations

Informed Consent was obtained from all participants. Participation was voluntary and based on anonymity. Students were instructed to respond honestly without fear of judgment or consequence. Data confidentiality was strictly maintained.

Delimitations

- ◆ The study was limited to male science students in public secondary schools in Faisalabad.
- ◆ Only two dimensions of scientific attitude : curiosity and rationality were analyzed in depth.

- ◆ Due to language barriers, some students found it challenging to interpret English-language questions.
- ◆ Logistical constraints (transportation, printing costs) were managed personally by the researcher.

Data Analysis and Results

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, weighted scores) to assess levels of curiosity and rationality among Grade 10 science students. Reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.719. Results indicated a moderate level of curiosity (grand mean = 3.54) and rationality (grand mean = 3.42). Despite interest in observable scientific phenomena, students displayed partial acceptance of rational thinking, with some responses influenced by superstitious beliefs. Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong, statistically significant positive relationships between curiosity and rationality ($r = .707, p < .01$), and between both constructs and overall scientific attitude, indicating their interdependence in shaping students' scientific dispositions

Curiosity

Curiosity, as a core component of scientific attitude, reflects an individual's desire to explore, question, and understand phenomena through observation and inquiry. In science education, curiosity plays a vital role in fostering engagement, conceptual learning, and long-term interest in scientific exploration (Engel, 2015; Jirout & Klahr, 2012). A five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) was used to assess students' curiosity-based attitudes toward science.

Table: 3

Distribution of the respondents according the scientific attitude of science students of scientific attitude in public sector on the basis of curiosity

Curiosity	W.S.	Mean	S.D.	Rank
I would like to know how our food gets digested in our body by watching internet videos.	663	4.09	1.141	1
I would get information that how Covid-19 is spreading rapidly.	585	3.61	1.110	2
I would like to know that why boiling water doesn't come out of pot but milk come out.	565	3.49	1.329	3
I would like to know the precautions about the Covid-19	547	3.38	1.347	4
I would like to know why it happened that under sun the water gets hotter and if we put tea under direct sun it doesn't remain hot so long.	509	3.14	1.478	5

Note: W.S. = Weighted Score; Mean = Average response; S.D. = Standard Deviation; Rank = Position based on mean score (1 = highest agreement). Scale: 1=strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5= strongly agree

The data show that students were generally curious, with a grand mean of 3.54, indicating a moderate level of curiosity. The highest-rated item (“I would like to know how our food gets digested...”) suggests that students are open to seeking scientific explanations, particularly using digital platforms, which aligns with findings by Chin and Osborne (2008) that digital inquiry supports curiosity in adolescents. However, lower-rated items involving abstract or less obvious scientific principles (e.g., thermodynamics of tea cooling) may indicate gaps in scientific reasoning or everyday conceptual understanding. These findings are consistent with Engel and Randall (2009), who argue that while curiosity is a natural trait in children, it often declines in formal educational settings unless actively nurtured

Figure: 2

Mean Responses of Students on Curiosity-Related Statements

Figure. 2 Graphical presentation of the respondents of scientific attitude in public sector on the basis of curiosity

Rationality

Rationality refers to the tendency to seek logical, evidence-based explanations over superstition or unverified beliefs. In science education, rational thinking is essential for hypothesis formation,

critical analysis, and decision-making (Braund & Reiss, 2006; Liu, Lin, & Tsai, 2011). Students were assessed using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).

Table: 3

Distribution of the respondents according the scientific attitude of science students of scientific attitude in public sector on the basis of Rationality

Rationality	W.S.	Mean	S.D.	Rank
I believe that a crying crow sitting on roof is a indication of guest arrival.	619	3.82	1.184	1
I believe that A black cat crossing the vehicles is a sign of misfortune to accident.	603	3.72	1.371	2
I would admit it if anything proves that drinking is injurious for health.	575	3.55	.978	3
I would avoid to go under the tree that night because I believe there lives a demon spirit.	513	3.17	1.509	4
I believe that shooting star could fulfill your wishes.	465	2.87	1.441	5

Note: W.S. = Weighted Score; Mean = Average response; S.D. = Standard Deviation; Rank = Position based on mean score (1 = highest agreement). Scale: 1=strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= strongly agree

The grand mean score was 3.42, suggesting a moderate level of rationality among students. Surprisingly, the most endorsed items reflected superstitious beliefs rather than scientific reasoning, indicating a persistent influence of cultural myths on student thinking. These findings align with Akpan and Andre (2020), who noted that scientific attitudes among students in developing contexts are often challenged by traditional beliefs. Although some students demonstrated a willingness to accept scientific evidence (e.g., regarding health risks), others continued to endorse unscientific views. This suggests a partial adoption of rationality, emphasizing the need for explicit instruction in critical thinking and evidence-based reasoning (Liu et al., 2011; Sahin et al., 2014).

Figure: 3

Mean Responses of Students on Rationality-Related Statements

Figure: 3 Graphical Presentation of the respondents of scientific attitude in public sector on the basis of Rationality

Table: 4

Pearson Correlations Among Scientific Attitude Dimensions (N = 162)

		Curiosity	Rationality	Scientific attitude
Curiosity	Pearson Correlation	1	.707**	.607**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	162	162	162
Rationality	Pearson Correlation	.707**	1	.669**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	162	162	162

Note: Pearson correlation coefficients. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data revealed strong and statistically significant correlations among all three constructs: A very strong positive correlation was found between Curiosity and Rationality ($r = .707$, $p < .01$), suggesting that students who are more inquisitive also tend to reason more logically and scientifically. This supports the idea that intellectual curiosity is deeply linked to rational, evidence-based thinking (Liu et al., 2011; Engel, 2015). Both Curiosity ($r = .607$, $p < .01$) and Rationality ($r = .669$, $p < .01$) showed strong, significant correlations with the overall scientific attitude composite score, indicating that these two dimensions are not only statistically interrelated, but are also essential contributors to a robust scientific mindset.

These findings are consistent with previous studies in science education showing that curiosity-driven learners tend to exhibit more critical thinking and scientific skepticism (Jirout & Klahr, 2012; Sahin et al., 2014). The mutual reinforcement between affective (curiosity) and cognitive (rationality) components reflects the multi-dimensional nature of scientific attitude as defined in contemporary science education framework.

Discussion

The findings of this study provided valuable insights into the scientific attitudes of Grade 10 science students in public secondary schools in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Two dimensions were examined in detail curiosity and rationality both of which are central to scientific dispositions. By empirically demonstrating the moderate but uneven development of scientific attitudes among secondary students in Faisalabad, this study highlights both the promise and the challenges of science education in Pakistan. Fostering curiosity and rationality is not just a matter of academic enrichment but a societal necessity, paving the way for a generation of learners who can think critically, challenge superstition, and contribute meaningfully to national progress in science and technology.

The results indicated that students demonstrated a moderate level of curiosity, with the highest-rated item reflecting interest in understanding biological processes such as digestion, supported by the use of digital platforms. This finding aligns with previous research showing that adolescent learners are naturally curious when scientific knowledge is presented as personally relevant and accessible (Engel, 2015; Chin & Osborne, 2008). However, curiosity was weaker for abstract or less observable scientific concepts (e.g., heat transfer in tea cooling), suggesting that inquiry-based pedagogies need to emphasize phenomena-based learning to sustain engagement (Jirout & Klahr, 2012).

Rationality results revealed a more complex pattern. While some students expressed willingness to accept scientific evidence, others continued to hold superstitious beliefs, such as linking animal behavior or celestial events to omens. These results underscore the tension between traditional cultural beliefs and formal science education, a pattern also reported by Akpan and Andre (2020). The moderate overall mean score for rationality indicates that science classrooms in this context are not yet fully equipping students to consistently apply evidence-based reasoning. This highlights a gap between the intended outcomes of the curriculum and the actual dispositions cultivated among learners.

Correlation analysis further showed strong positive relationships between curiosity, rationality, and the overall scientific attitude composite score. This supports the theoretical proposition that affective (curiosity) and cognitive (rationality) dimensions are interdependent (Sahin et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2011). In other words, when students are encouraged to explore, they are also more likely to develop rational thinking skills, and vice versa. Additionally, significant correlations with age and income suggest that developmental stage and socioeconomic status remain important factors influencing scientific dispositions, consistent with earlier meta-analyses (Sirin, 2005; Gopalan & Chapman, 2016).

Conclusion

This study set out to measure the scientific attitudes of secondary-level science students in Faisalabad, Pakistan, focusing on curiosity and rationality. The findings show that while students exhibit a moderate curiosity toward science, their rationality remains uneven, with persistence of traditional superstitions alongside partial acceptance of scientific reasoning. Both dimensions were strongly correlated with each other and with overall scientific attitude, underscoring their mutually reinforcing role in shaping learners' scientific outlook.

Thus, the study concluded that scientific curiosity is emerging among adolescents, but rationality requires more deliberate cultivation through critical thinking exercises, inquiry-based instruction, and explicit engagement with everyday beliefs. Strengthening these dispositions is essential not only for academic achievement but also for preparing students to contribute to a scientifically literate society.

Implications for Practice

The analysis revealed that while students exhibit a moderate level of scientific curiosity, their rationality is compromised by superstitious thinking. This duality reflects the tension between formal science education and deep-rooted cultural beliefs, particularly in socio-economically constrained environments. As Tuan, Chin, and Shieh (2005) emphasize, scientific attitude development requires not just content delivery but active engagement with epistemological beliefs, including rejection of pseudo-scientific notions. Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping scientific attitudes by promoting inquiry, encouraging questioning, and challenging irrational beliefs in classroom discussions. Structured interventions that foster curiosity and critical thinking are essential for long-term attitude change. Curriculum designers should recognize curiosity and rationality as interdependent constructs that must be nurtured together through inquiry-based and reasoning-centered science instruction. Teachers should promote classroom environments where questioning, exploration, and logic-based reasoning are valued and rewarded. Interventions aiming to improve scientific literacy should simultaneously develop students' dispositional curiosity and analytical reasoning skills.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

While this study made an important contribution, several limitations should be acknowledged,

- Geographical scope: Data were limited to male students from public schools in Faisalabad; results cannot be generalized to female students or private institutions.
- Self-reported data: Reliance on Likert-scale questionnaires may introduce social desirability bias.
- Cross-sectional design: The study captures attitudes at a single point in time and cannot assess changes over time.

- Language barriers: Some students faced difficulty interpreting English-language items, which may have influenced responses. Future research could address these limitations by expanding samples across genders, school types, and regions.
- Using mixed methods (e.g., interviews, classroom observations) to capture nuanced attitudes.
- Conducting longitudinal studies to track changes in scientific dispositions over time while testing the effectiveness of interventions designed to strengthen curiosity and rationality in science classrooms.

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